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Thermal and energy Management for INcreased Driving range of an Electric minibus including improved user-centric Design and thermal comfort

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D5.1: Measurement results of initial vehicle identification (PU)

Publishable Executive Summary

The **target of the European MINDED project** is to deliver a (virtual) concept for a battery-electric, zero-emission IVECO eDaily minibus with 20 % improved range at 0 °C ambient temperature. This improvement will be achieved through several advanced technologies.

To get a reliable database, the series-production status of the minibus was measured on the vehicle chassis dynamometer in the climatic chamber at ATC. The test program was defined in deliverable D1.1.

During the tests, vehicle parameters with focus on passenger thermal comfort and energy consumption were measured as defined in deliverable D1.1. (WP1). The results will be used for further investigations and deliver the main input for the activities under WP2, WP3, WP4.

For the baseline measurements, the following quantities were evaluated for each use case:

- Energy consumption – isolated and overall consumption
- Real-world range (WLTP-based)
- Cool down curves of the minibus cabin
- Cabin and comfort related quantities
 - Temperatures in the cabin
 - Comfort index – Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)

The main findings for the tests at 0 °C, which is the relevant ambient temperature for the MINDED project, are:

- An **overall energy consumption of 77.2 kWh** results, leading to a **real-world range** (WLTP based) of **161 km**.
- Thermal parameters were extracted from the cool down curves
- The **set temperature of +23 °C cannot be reached in the cabin**, although the heating of the driver and the passengers was switched on during the whole measurement. Consequently, **thermal comfort** (indicated by the PMV-index) **cannot be reached**. However, it is worth to mention that in its standard configuration, the minibus is equipped with an additional fuel-powered heater, to ensure passenger comfort at low ambient temperatures. But, following the zero-emission project strategy, it was switched off for all tests.

The above highlighted values serve as a basis for the further steps in the project. In the following deliverables D5.3 and D5.4, these quantities recorded on improved versions of the bus will be compared to identify the gained improvements.

Justification of Postponement of Deadline

The minibus of MINDED was delivered with a delay. This was because there were some changes in the production of the bus and IVECO had to find a suitable vehicle for the project. Furthermore, once the bus was on site, there were problems with the powertrain which had to be fixed in a workshop. Therefore, as much work as possible was prepared in advance for the measurements. The measurement plan and use cases were prepared, the measurement equipment was ordered, and everything was set for the measurements. One the bus arrived the measurement equipment could be integrated into the bus. However, due to maintenance work and an unforeseen closure of the dynamometer, the measurements had to be further postponed. Hence, a postponement of the deadline of this deliverable from 06/2024 to 11/2024 was requested and granted on May 31st, 2024.

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D5.1: Measurement results of initial vehicle identification (PU)

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Test setup.....	7
2.1	Vehicle.....	7
2.2	Measurement Program – Driving Cycle, Use Cases, HVAC settings	8
2.2.1	Driving Cycle	8
2.2.2	Use Cases.....	8
2.2.3	HVAC settings in vehicle	9
2.3	Data acquisition	10
2.3.1	CAN Bus measurement	10
2.3.2	Additionally added sensors.....	10
2.4	Dynamometer Settings	10
3	Measurement results – vehicle baseline / basic conditions	11
3.1	Energy consumption.....	11
3.1.1	Energy consumption of drivetrain	11
3.1.2	Energy consumption of PTC-Cabin-Heater and PTC-Passenger Heater.....	12
3.1.3	Energy consumption of PTC-Battery Heater.....	13
3.1.4	Energy consumption of compressor	14
3.1.5	Energy consumption of Low Voltage-System DC/DC.....	14
3.1.6	Overall energy consumption.....	15
3.2	Real-World Range (WLTP based)	16
3.3	Cool Down Curves	16
3.4	Cabin and comfort measurements	17
3.4.1	Temperatures in the cabin.....	18
3.4.2	UC 1 (-7 °C)	18
3.4.3	UC 2 (0 °C).....	18
3.4.4	UC 3 (23 °C).....	19
3.4.5	UC 4 (40 °C).....	20
3.4.6	Comfort index – Predicted Mean Vote (PMV).....	21
3.4.7	UC 1 (-7 °C)	22
3.4.8	UC 2 (0 °C).....	23
3.4.9	UC 3 (23 °C).....	23
3.4.10	UC 4 (40 °C).....	24
4	Conclusions	26
5	Acknowledgment.....	28

List of Figures

Figure 1: IVECO eDAILY Minibus.....	7
Figure 2: WLTP Class 2 velocity comparison.....	8
Figure 3: WLTP Class 2 distance comparison.....	8
Figure 4: Vehicle on the dynamometer of ATC.....	10
Figure 5: Layout of the electrical system.....	11
Figure 6: Energy consumption of the drivetrain.....	12
Figure 7: Energy consumption of the PTC Cabin Heater.....	12
Figure 8: Energy consumption of the PTC Passenger Heater.....	13
Figure 9: Energy consumption of the PTC Battery Heater.....	13
Figure 10: Energy consumption of the compressor.....	14
Figure 11: Energy consumption of the low voltage system (DC/DC).....	15
Figure 12: Overall energy consumption.....	15
Figure 13: Real-world range (WLTP based).....	16
Figure 14: Cooldown curves at different ambient temperatures.....	17
Figure 15: Positions of the comfort measurement dummies and temperature sensors in the cabin.....	17
Figure 16: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at -7 °C ambient temperature.....	18
Figure 17: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at 0 °C ambient temperature.....	19
Figure 18: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at +23 °C ambient temperature.....	20
Figure 19: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at +40 °C ambient temperature.....	20
Figure 20: Predicted Mean Vote index scale.....	21
Figure 21: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at -7 °C ambient temperature.....	22
Figure 22: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at 0 °C ambient temperature.....	23
Figure 23: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at +23 °C ambient temperature.....	24
Figure 24: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at +40 °C ambient temperature.....	25

List of Tables

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Nomenclature.....	5
Table 2: Relevant information for the test vehicle.....	7
Table 3: Use cases (UC) for vehicle measurements.....	9
Table 4: HVAC settings in the vehicle.....	9

Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Symbol or Shortname	Description
AC	Alternating current / Air conditioning system
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
CAN	Controller area network
DC	Direct current
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HV	High voltage
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IR	Infrared
LV	Low voltage
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
PTC	Positive temperature coefficient
SOC	State of charge
UC	Use case
WLTP	Worldwide harmonized Light Vehicles Test Procedure

1 Introduction

The **target of the European MINDED project** is to deliver a (virtual) concept for a battery-electric, zero-emission IVECO eDaily minibus with 20 % improved range at 0 °C ambient temperature. This target should be reached through a highly efficient heating system for the driver and passengers based on *infrared (IR) heating panels*, controlled by an *optimal thermal and energy management strategy*, supported by an *innovative human-machine interface (HMI)*, an *optimised air conditioning system* in heat pump mode using an *innovative oil-free centrifugal e-compressor* with gas bearing technology. The performance of the implemented heating system will be demonstrated on a chassis dynamometer at 0 °C ambient temperature at TRL 7, while the air conditioning system performance in heat pump mode will be demonstrated on the ThermoLab testbed under various operating conditions at TRL 6.

To further improve the performance of the IVECO eDaily minibus, an *overall predictive thermal and energy management strategy will be demonstrated in the Digital Twin Model of the entire vehicle*. The model considers the vehicle's powertrain, the implemented infrared heating and the air conditioning systems, and a prediction of the driving behaviour based on artificial intelligence (AI) and Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) sensors.

The ambition of MINDED involves the development, implementation, and demonstration of technologies at TRL 6-7, with 20 % improved real-world range at 0 °C ambient temperature compared to the baseline battery-electric IVECO eDaily minibus. MINDED developments aim at a cost reduction of at least 5 % at vehicle level and a reduction of development time by 30 % through digital twin and AI deployment, while increasing the performance and reliability.

Deliverable **D5.1 Measurement results of initial vehicle identification** is related to WP5 "Implementation, demonstration, and assessment on vehicle level" and is under responsibility of ATC, collecting the contributions from AIT, ATC and TUW. It reports the measurement results of the IVECO eDaily minibus in its basic conditions on the vehicle chassis dynamometer in the climate chamber at ATC, where vehicle parameters with focus on passenger thermal comfort were measured as defined in WP1, especially in D1.1. These measurement results define the base results for further investigations and planned improvements and deliver the main input for the activities under WP2, WP3, WP4.

2 Test setup

The test setup describes the vehicle settings, the measurement program including the used driving cycle as well as the different use cases, the data acquisition and the testbed settings which were used and required for determination of the baseline measurement and the status quo of the IVECO MINDED bus.

2.1 Vehicle

The test vehicle is an IVECO electric minibus as shown below in Figure 1. It is equipped with a suspended e-motor with 140 kW peak power and 90 kW continuous power (400 Nm peak torque and 220 Nm continuous torque) that transmits power to the rear axle through a centre differential. The selected version is set up with three battery packs for a total energy storage of 111 kWh. Recharging is possible in AC mode and up to 40 kW in DC mode. The vehicle has 22 passenger seats arranged on 7 seat rows plus driver seat.

Figure 1: IVECO eDAILY Minibus.

The following Table 2 provides relevant information for the test vehicle provided by IVECO, needed to set up the chassis dynamometer (see chapter 2.4) and documents the status of the minibus. Road load parameters as well as test masses were provided by IVECO.

Table 2: Relevant information for the test vehicle.

Road load parameters	
F0	980.0 N
F1	0.0 N/(km/h)
F2	0.1115 N/(km/h) ²
Masses	
Testmass	7,000 kg
Mass in running order	4,580 kg
Tires	
Brand	Continental
Type	VancoFourSeason 2
Wheel dimensions front and rear:	225/75 R16 C
Wheel pressure front: rear:	4.0 bar 5.2 bar
Tire tread depth front left: front right: rear left inside / outside: rear right inside / outside:	4.0 mm 3.7 mm 2.2 mm / 2.9 mm 1.9 mm / 2.0 mm

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D5.1: Measurement results of initial vehicle identification (PU)

2.2 Measurement Program – Driving Cycle, Use Cases, HVAC settings

2.2.1 Driving Cycle

For determining the energy consumption and having a comparable measure for all developments in the project, a standardised driving cycle was used for the measurements on the chassis dynamometer of ATC. Since the call asked for a 20 % increase of the “real-world range” at 0 °C, the Worldwide harmonized Light Vehicles Test Procedure (WLTP) cycle was selected and used as the cycle to determine this increase. The WLTP is a global driving cycle standard for determining the all-electric range of electric vehicles. It is close to a real-world cycle and easily replicated. As there is no special driving cycle for an electric minibus, the consortium decided to use the WLTP (which is standard for passenger cars and vans) as the reference cycle in MINDED.

Figure 2: WLTP Class 2 velocity comparison.

As the class of WLTP, in which the vehicle falls into, is defined over the ratio of rated engine power divided by mass, the minibus falls in the category of WLTP class 2. Furthermore, as the maximum speed of the bus is limited to 85 km/h it was decided, that the WLTP class 2 cycle must be capped at 85 km/h and the maximum speed is driven until the driving distance of the uncapped WLTP class 2 of 22.649 km is reached. The resulting driving cycle compared to the original one is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 3: WLTP Class 2 distance comparison.

2.2.2 Use Cases

The main temperature which is relevant for all developments in MINDED is 0 °C. This value is stated in the projects’ call and therefore, results (increase of driving range of by at least 20 %) must be shown for this temperature. In order to parameterise the simulation models and validate the functionality and accuracy of the

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models, additional ambient temperatures are necessary. As there are basically no limitations of the climatic chamber containing the chassis dynamometer (possible temperature range between -35 °C up to +50 °C) suitable temperatures had to be defined. In accordance with IVECO standard measurement procedures, following ambient temperatures were selected for measurement on the chassis dynamometer:

- Use case 1: -7 °C
- Use case 2: 0 °C
- Use case 3: 23 °C
- Use case 4: 40 °C

The target aimed for the end of the test in deliverable D1.1 was a steady state of the cabin temperature at 23 °C. A fixed number of 5 cycles was selected as the test stop criteria. The use cases are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Use cases (UC) for vehicle measurements.

	Unit	UC 1	UC 2	UC 3	UC 4
Ambient Temp.	°C	- 7	0	+ 23	+ 40
Cabin Temp.	°C	+ 23	+ 23	+ 23	+ 23
Cycle	-	WLTP class 2 capped	WLTP class 2 capped	WLTP class 2 capped	WLTP class 2 capped
Nr. of driven cycles	-	5	5	5	5
SOC Start	%	100	100	100	100
Stop Crit.	-	after 5 th cycle	after 5 th cycle	after 5 th cycle	after 5 th cycle
Humidity	%	Cannot be set in climatic chamber for these temperatures		50	20
Mass		All use cases with empty bus (no passengers but driver) but simulated full bus by setting the mass as dyno resistance.			

2.2.3 HVAC settings in vehicle

The aim was a realistic manner of usage, to simulate a realistic user behaviour in the minibus. Generally, the driver can control the following HVAC-systems:

- Driver Area Heating and Cooling
- Passenger Area Heating
- Passenger Area Cooling

To guarantee repeatable and comparable results among the different measurements and test phases, the settings of the HVAC system were defined and used as shown in Table 4.

At this point, it should be highlighted, that the minibus is equipped with a fuel-powered additional heater in its standard configuration, to ensure passenger comfort at low ambient temperatures. For the MINDED project and to ensure the zero-emissions project strategy, this heater was deactivated for all tests.

Table 4: HVAC settings in the vehicle.

Device / Use cases	UC 1: -7 °C	UC 2: 0 °C	UC 3: +23 °C	UC 4: +40 °C
Driver Area Heating	+23 °C Auto / AC	+23 °C Auto / AC	OFF	+23 °C Auto / AC
Passenger Area Cooling	OFF	OFF	OFF	+23 °C Auto
Passenger Area Heating	ON (no temp. Setting)	ON (no temp. Setting)	OFF	OFF

2.3 Data acquisition

2.3.1 CAN Bus measurement

Modern vehicles are equipped with several control units. Its aim is to observe and control the function of the corresponding parts of the vehicle. For that purpose, a lot of sensors are used. To transfer the large amount of data from one control unit to another, CAN busses are used. The CAN bus offers a convenient method for collecting measurement data using the built-in sensors. To be able to use the data for the calculations and simulations within the project, the minibus was equipped with a CAN logger by IVECO. This device is logging all available channels throughout the tests.

2.3.2 Additionally added sensors

Although, there is a lot of data on the CAN Bus, further measurement devices were required. In each coolant circuit, a volume flow sensor was implemented. Moreover, in the powertrain coolant circuit, coolant temperature sensors were added before and after the relevant components (DC/DC, Inverter, Motor). In the battery coolant circuit, a coolant temperature sensor was added after the battery packs. Furthermore, in the driver and passenger heating circuits, coolant temperature sensors were installed before and after the heat exchanger, along with an air temperature sensor at the air outlet in the cabin. Together with the built-in sensors, this allows the accurate calculation of the heat flow from the components to the coolant circuits, which is the basis for digital twin model parameterization and the ThermoLab testbench investigations. All analogue measurement signals originating from the sensors implemented into the thermal systems and the cabin of the bus are recorded with the imc Cronos-PL-16 measurement system.

2.4 Dynamometer Settings

The purpose of the roller dynamometer is to simulate the driving resistance that occurs during a vehicle's operation. Additionally, as the roller dynamometer is in a climatic chamber, constant environmental conditions (temperature, humidity) can be guaranteed. For the MINDED project it is used to measure the energy consumption of the vehicle and simulate environmental conditions for the different use cases.

The chassis dynamometer was set up¹ according to the data in Table 2, with respect to the road load and test mass of the minibus. For each test, the environmental conditions (temperature and - where possible - humidity) were adjusted according to Table 3. The minibus was soaked overnight at each ambient temperature, to ensure stable temperature conditions within all parts of the vehicle (cabin, battery, etc.). Immediately before test start, the HVAC-system was activated according to Table 4. These settings were not changed during the test. As the bus offers different drive modes (eco, normal, power), the tests were driven in “normal” mode, without switching off ignition between each cycle. The following Figure 4 shows the IVECO electric minibus on the chassis dynamometer at ATC.

Figure 4: Vehicle on the dynamometer of ATC.

¹ Road load adaption according to EU-reg. 2017/1151 as amended by 2023/443

3 Measurement results – vehicle baseline / basic conditions

3.1 Energy consumption

In this chapter, the energy consumption measured for various components is presented for the four use cases. These components include the drivetrain, PTC heaters for the cabin, passenger compartment and battery as well as the compressor, the DC/DC converter and the battery's overall energy supply. Figure 5 illustrates the layout of the electrical system, divided into high-voltage and low-voltage side.

Figure 5: Layout of the electrical system.

In the following pages, the energy consumption of each high-voltage component will be analysed, and the impact of ambient temperature on the energy demand will be discussed. The measurement results will be presented as box plots, displaying the minimum, maximum, and average energy consumption recorded during the measurement campaign. As two tests were driven at each temperature, the results reflect the mean value of the two tests at each temperature. The deviations from the mean value are reflected by error bars. Additionally, potential strategies for reducing consumption will be outlined.

3.1.1 Energy consumption of drivetrain

In this chapter, the drivetrain's energy consumption is analysed. Figure 6 presents the measurement results across the use cases. The highest consumption, 61 kWh, occurs at -7 °C (UC 1), with a clear trend of decreasing consumption as the ambient temperature rises, reaching a minimum of 51.5 kWh at +40 °C (UC 4). This trend can be attributed to increased drivetrain efficiency as well as reduced driving resistance, with rolling resistance in particular being closely linked to tire temperature.

Figure 6: Energy consumption of the drivetrain.

3.1.2 Energy consumption of PTC-Cabin-Heater and PTC-Passenger Heater

Figure 7 and Figure 8 illustrate the energy consumption of the PTC cabin heater and the PTC passenger heater for the use cases. The PTC heaters are responsible for heating the air in the driver and passenger compartments, respectively. At ambient temperatures of +23 °C (UC 3) and above, interior heating is not necessary, resulting in zero energy consumption. At -7 °C (UC 1) and 0 °C (UC 2), however, interior heating requires 5.9 to 6.6 kWh for the cabin heater and 9.5 to 10.4 kWh for the passenger heater.

Figure 7: Energy consumption of the PTC Cabin Heater.

Figure 8: Energy consumption of the PTC Passenger Heater.

Within this project, the energy consumption shall be reduced, by means of implementing a more efficient heating system, improving the cabin insulation and optimizing the thermal management strategy.

3.1.3 Energy consumption of PTC-Battery Heater

In this chapter, the energy consumption of the battery PTC heater is discussed. At +23 °C (UC 3) and +40 °C (UC 4), the battery heater remains inactive. At lower temperatures, however, the battery requires heating, resulting in an energy consumption of 2 kWh at -7 °C (UC 1) and 1.3 kWh at 0 °C (UC 2), respectively.

Figure 9: Energy consumption of the PTC Battery Heater.

At low battery temperature, the operation of the battery is severely restricted. Both the maximum discharging and the maximum charging current are reduced. For discharging, the increased internal resistance at low temperature reduces the maximum possible power output, whereas for charging, the power must be reduced drastically to protect the battery from degradation (lithium-plating). Therefore, recuperative braking is limited in this operating zone. Through heating, the battery can be protected, the maximum possible discharge power

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can be increased, recuperative braking can be enabled, and the efficiency can be increased. However, heating comes with a substantial energy demand, indicating that there is an optimal trade-off in battery heating.

To minimize energy demand, this project will implement a predictive battery thermal and energy management strategy.

3.1.4 Energy consumption of compressor

In this chapter, the energy consumption of the compressor for the four use cases is analysed. Figure 10 presents the measurement results. At -7 °C (UC 1), 0 °C (UC 2), and +23 °C (UC 3), the energy consumption is zero due to the absence of any cooling requirements for both the battery and the cabin. Conversely, at +40 °C (UC 4), cooling is required for both the cabin and the battery, resulting in a significant energy demand of 6.2 kWh.

While the cabin cooling is primarily for passenger comfort, battery cooling serves two critical purposes: preventing overheating and reducing battery aging.

Figure 10: Energy consumption of the compressor.

To reduce the compressor's energy demand, several approaches can be considered: enhancing cabin insulation, adopting more efficient compressor technology, or optimizing the thermal management strategy for cabin and battery cooling.

3.1.5 Energy consumption of Low Voltage-System DC/DC

Figure 11 shows the energy supplied to the DC/DC converter. At +23 °C (UC 3) the measurements show a value of 1.1 kWh. As the temperature decreases, consumption increases to 1.5 kWh at 0 °C (UC 2) and 1.6 kWh at -7 °C (UC 1). The highest measured consumption, 3.8 kWh, occurred at +40 °C (UC 4).

The DC/DC converter powers the low-voltage electrical system, which includes the coolant pumps, blowers, radiator fan, and low-voltage cabin PTC heater. At low temperatures, the coolant pumps and blowers operate at high power to distribute the heat generated by the PTC heaters throughout the vehicle and its components, resulting in elevated DC/DC consumption. Similarly, at high temperatures, these components run to cool both the vehicle and its components. Additionally, the radiator fan at the front of the vehicle operates to ensure proper condensation of the refrigerant, leading to the highest consumption across the use cases.

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Figure 11: Energy consumption of the low voltage system (DC/DC).

In this project, a predictive energy and thermal management strategy will be implemented, to reduce the consumption of low-voltage components. This strategy optimizes component operation to meet temperature goals while minimizing energy demand.

3.1.6 Overall energy consumption

The overall energy consumption is shown in Figure 12. The minimum energy consumption of 54.9 kWh occurs in UC 3 at an ambient temperature of +23 °C. This is primarily due to the absence of energy demand for cabin conditioning and battery heating, as well as the relatively high efficiency and low driving resistances at this medium temperature. As the ambient temperature decreases, driving resistances increase, and the energy demand for heating the cabin and components rises, resulting in a maximum energy consumption of 81.6 kWh at -7 °C (UC 1).

Figure 12: Overall energy consumption.

When the ambient temperature increases, driving resistances are reduced, but the overall energy demand increases due to the need for cabin and battery cooling, including the operation of the radiator fan and the compressor. Consequently, at +40 °C (UC 4), the energy consumption of 61.5 kWh is significantly higher than at +23 °C (UC 3).

At 0 °C (UC 2), which is the relevant ambient temperature for the MINDED project, the measured energy consumption was 77.2 kWh.

3.2 Real-World Range (WLTP based)

The overall energy consumption presented in the previous chapter (3.1) is reflected in the real-world range of the minibus shown in Figure 1. It is calculated as a theoretical value, using the energy consumption of the high voltage system (Figure 12) for 5 WLTCs (total distance of approx. 112 km) and the theoretical energy content of the batteries of 111 kWh.

At +23 °C (UC 3), the maximum range of 226 km is achieved. At -7 °C (UC 1), 0 °C (UC 2), and +40 °C (UC 4), the range is reduced compared to the +23 °C case. The minimum possible range occurs at an ambient temperature of -7 °C (UC 1).

The relevant temperature for the MINDED project is 0 °C (UC 2). Here, the real-world range of the baseline vehicle is 161 km.

Figure 13: Real-world range (WLTP based).

3.3 Cool Down Curves

During the measurements, cooldown curves were recorded while recharging the vehicle. The cooldown curve of a vehicle, following Newton's Law of Cooling, describes the rate at which the temperature inside the vehicle cabin approaches the ambient temperature over time. Newton's Law of Cooling states that the rate of change of temperature of an object is proportional to the temperature difference between the object and its surroundings.

$$T(t) = T_{ambient} + (T_0 - T_{ambient}) \cdot e^{-\tau \cdot t}$$

Where T(t) is the cabin temperature at time t, $T_{ambient}$ is the ambient temperature, T_0 the initial temperature of the cabin at time t=0, τ is the cooling constant and t is the time elapsed. The rate of cooling depends on the constant τ , which in turn depends on factors as the heat capacity and the thermal resistance to the environment. With this, the initial thermal validation of the cabin model can be conducted.

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Figure 14: Cooldown curves at different ambient temperatures.

3.4 Cabin and comfort measurements

In this chapter, the results of the cabin and comfort measurements are presented for the four use cases. This includes the temperatures in the cabin as well as the comfort index (Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)). Figure 15 illustrates the positions of the comfort measurement dummies and temperature sensors in the cabin of the minibus.

Figure 15: Positions of the comfort measurement dummies and temperature sensors in the cabin.

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3.4.1 Temperatures in the cabin

3.4.2 UC 1 (-7 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 16 show the temperatures of the three dummies and the temperatures along the isle according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of -7 °C (UC 1). Even though the heating of the driver and the passengers are switched on during the whole measurement (set temperature: +23 °C, according to Table 4), the maximum temperature reached at the end is roughly +15 °C. Dummy 1 experiences higher temperatures at the legs, as the radiator is right under this seat.

Figure 16: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at -7 °C ambient temperature.

3.4.3 UC 2 (0 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 17 show the temperatures of the three dummies and the temperatures along the isle according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of 0 °C (UC 2).

Even though the heating of the driver and the passengers are switched on during the whole measurement (set temperature: +23 °C, according to Table 4), the maximum temperature reached at the end is roughly +18 °C. Dummy 1 experiences higher temperatures at the legs, as the radiator is right under this seat.

Figure 17: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at 0 °C ambient temperature.

3.4.4 UC 3 (23 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 18 show the temperatures of the three dummies and the temperatures along the isle according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of +23 °C (UC 3).

The heating of the driver and the passengers as well as the air conditioning system are switched off during the whole measurement. The temperature in the cabin rises only slightly.

Figure 18: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at +23 °C ambient temperature.

3.4.5 UC 4 (40 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 19 show the temperatures of the three dummies and the temperatures along the isle according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of +40 °C (UC 4).

As the graphs indicate, the set temperature of the AC system of +23 °C (according to Table 4) is reached at all 4 shown measurement points. Due to the strategy of the AC system, the cooling is switched on and off. Therefore, the temperatures in the figures below show some peaks.

Figure 19: Temperatures of the Dummies at different body positions and the temperature along the isle at +40 °C ambient temperature.

3.4.6 Comfort index – Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)

Thermal comfort is a key issue in the project MINDED. Therefore, the objective determination of the thermal comfort is a very important task, needed for the evaluations of the implementations done during the project. Measuring thermal comfort is difficult, but there exists an index, which represents the comfort of a human being. This is the so called Predicted Mean Vote index, developed by Fanger². The PMV is an index that represents the average value for climate assessment by a large group of people using the following 7-step climate assessment scale (see Figure 20). The PMV index is based on the thermal balance of the human body. Thermal equilibrium is reached when the heat generated by the body is equal to the heat given off to the environment. In a moderate ambient climate, the human thermoregulation system automatically changes the skin temperature and sweat secretion to maintain thermal balance³.

Figure 20: Predicted Mean Vote index scale.

PMV values are calculated with following parameters and formulas:

- metabolism constant (met): 58.1 W/m²
- metabolic rate (M): 1.12 met
- rate of mechanical work (W): 0 W
- clothing constant (clo): 0.155
- clothing resistance (I_{cl}): 1 clo (medium clothing for -7 °C and 0 °C), 0.5 clo (light clothing for +23 °C and +40 °C)
- globe diameter for calculation of mean radiant temperature: 0.08 m

$$PMV = [0.303 \cdot e^{(-0.036 \cdot M)} + 0.028] \cdot \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (M - W) - 3.05 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot [5733 - 6.99 \cdot (M - W) - p_a] - 0.42[(M - W) - 58.15] \\ -1.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M \cdot (5867 - p_a) - 0.0014 \cdot M \cdot (34 - t_a) \\ -3.96 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot f_{cl}[(t_{cl} + 273)^4 - (MRT + 273)^4] - f_{cl} \cdot h_c \cdot (t_{cl} - t_a) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

$$t_{cl} = 35.7 - 0.028(M - W) - I_{cl}\{3.96 \cdot 10^{-8} f_{cl}[(t_{cl} + 273)^4 - (MRT + 273)^4] + f_{cl} h_c(t_{cl} - t_a)\} \quad (2)$$

$$h_c = \begin{cases} 2.38 \cdot |t_{cl} - t_a|^{0.25} & \text{for } 2.38 \cdot |t_{cl} - t_a|^{0.25} \cdot U \cdot 12.1 \cdot \sqrt{v_{ar}} \\ 12.1 \cdot \sqrt{v_{ar}} & \text{for } 2.38 \cdot |t_{cl} - t_a|^{0.25} \cdot I \cdot 12.1 \cdot \sqrt{v_{ar}} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$f_{cl} = \begin{cases} 1.00 + 1.290 \cdot I_{cl} & \text{for } I_{cl} \leq 0.078 m^2 \cdot K/W \\ 1.05 + 0.645 \cdot I_{cl} & \text{for } I_{cl} > 0.078 m^2 \cdot K/W \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$p_a = RH \cdot 10 \cdot e^{\frac{16.6536 - 4030.183}{t_a + 235}} \quad (5)$$

² Fanger O., “Thermal Comfort,” 1970.

³ Ergonomics of the thermal environment – Analytical determination and interpretation of thermal comfort using calculation of the PMV and PPD indices and local thermal comfort criteria (ISO 7730:2005)

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D5.1: Measurement results of initial vehicle identification (PU)

Where:

- M is the metabolic rate.
- W is the rate of mechanical work.
- I_{cl} is the insulation of the clothing.
- f_{cl} is the area factor of the clothing.
- t_a is the ambient temperature.
- MRT is the mean radiant temperature.
- v_{ar} is the air velocity.
- p_a is the water vapor pressure.
- h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient.
- t_{cl} is the surface temperature of the clothing.

The dummies were sitting on three distributed seats in the cabin according to the measurement plan in Figure 15. Each dummy consists of three measurement positions – Leg, Body, and Head – where ambient temperature, humidity, and mean radiant temperature are measured. The air flow velocity was measured with a handheld anemometer, as the settings are always the same and the flow velocity are always lower than 0.1 m/s. Dummy 1 next to the radiator actually experiences higher flow velocities on the Leg, but as this velocity only influences the mean radiant temperature this was neglected, as the temperature of the air coming out of the radiator is much higher and therefore has a larger influence on the PMV.

3.4.7 UC 1 (-7 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 21 show the PMV indices of the three dummies according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of -7 °C.

Figure 21: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at -7 °C ambient temperature.

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Even though the heating of the driver and the passengers are switched on during the whole measurement, thermal comfort (the green area indicating the comfort zone) cannot be reached until the end of the measurement, except for the leg of Dummy 1 sitting right next to the radiator.

3.4.8 UC 2 (0 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 22 show the PMV indices of the three dummies according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of 0 °C.

Even though the heating of the driver and the passengers are switched on during the whole measurement, thermal comfort (the green area indicating the comfort zone) cannot be reached until the end of the measurement, except for the leg of Dummy 1 sitting right next to the radiator, which in fact is too hot at the end of the measurement.

Figure 22: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at 0 °C ambient temperature.

3.4.9 UC 3 (23 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 23 show the PMV indices of the three dummies according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of +23 °C.

All dummies are in thermal comfort during the entire measurement.

Figure 23: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at +23 °C ambient temperature.

3.4.10 UC 4 (40 °C)

The following subfigures of Figure 24 show the PMV indices of the three dummies according to the plan in Figure 15 at an ambient temperature of +40 °C.

All dummies are nearly in thermal comfort at the end. Dummy 2 and Dummy 3 are a little bit too cold.

Figure 24: PMV index of the Dummies at different body positions at +40 °C ambient temperature.

4 Conclusions

The **target of the European MINDED project** is to deliver a (virtual) concept for battery-electric, zero-emission IVECO eDaily minibus with a 20 % improved range at 0 °C ambient temperature. This improvement will be achieved through advanced technologies, including:

- **Efficient Heating System:** Utilizing infrared (IR) heating panels, optimized thermal and energy management strategies and an innovative human-machine interface (HMI).
- **Advanced Air Conditioning:** Incorporating a heat pump system with an oil-free centrifugal e-compressor using gas bearing technology.
- **Predictive Thermal and Energy Management:** Employing a digital twin model that integrates the vehicle's systems with AI and Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) to optimize energy usage based on driving predictions.

To get a reliable database, the series-production status of the minibus was measured on the vehicle chassis dynamometer in the climate chamber at ATC. The test program was defined in deliverable D1.1. The main parts are:

- 4 use cases: -7 °C, 0 °C, +23 °C, +40 °C
- Drive cycle: 5 consecutive WLTP class 2 capped speed cycles
- Defined settings of the HVAC-system

During the tests, vehicle parameters with focus on passenger thermal comfort were measured as defined in deliverable D1.1. (WP1). The results will be used for further investigations and deliver the main input for the activities under WP2, WP3, WP4.

For the baseline measurements, the following quantities were evaluated (and depicted in this deliverable) for each use case:

- Energy consumption of
 - Drivetrain
 - PTC-Cabin-Heater and PTC-Passenger-Heater
 - PTC-Battery Heater
 - Compressor
 - Low Voltage-System DC/DC
- Overall energy consumption as a sum of the single consumers above
- Real-world range (WLTP-based)
- Cool Down Curves of the minibus cabin
- Cabin and Comfort related quantities
 - Temperatures in the cabin
 - Comfort index – Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)

For the tests at 0 °C (UC 2), which is the relevant ambient temperature for the MINDED project, the findings are:

- The **energy consumptions** of the isolated components are:
 - Drivetrain: 59.1 kWh
 - PTC-Cabin-Heater and PTC-Passenger-Heater: 5.9 and 9.5 kWh
 - PTC-Battery Heater: 1.3 kWh
 - Compressor: 0.0 kWh
 - Low Voltage-System DC/DC: 1.5 kWh
- The above data reflects an **overall energy consumption** of **77.2 kWh**, yielding a **real-world range** (WLTP-based) of **161 km**.

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D5.1: Measurement results of initial vehicle identification (PU)

- A model for simulating the cool down curve was established. With this, the initial thermal validation of the cabin model can be conducted.
- As further investigations show, the **set temperature of +23 °C cannot be reached in the cabin** although the heating of the driver and the passengers is switched on during the whole measurement. Consequently, **thermal comfort** (indicated by the PMV-index) **cannot be reached**. However, it is worth mentioning, that in its standard configuration, the minibus is equipped with an additional fuel-powered heater, to ensure passenger comfort at low ambient temperatures. But, following the zero-emission project strategy, it was switched off for all tests.
- Therefore, it will be necessary to extrapolate the heating consumption until thermal comfort in the cabin is reached. Only then a fair comparison with all future improvements can be drawn, as it is likely, that with the improvements thermal comfort will be reached.

The above highlighted values serve as a basis for the further development in the project. In the following deliverables D5.3 and D5.4, these quantities will be compared, to identify the gained improvements.

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D5.1: Measurement results of initial vehicle identification (PU)